

ON THE CERTIFICATION OF BONDED COMPOSITE REPAIRS TO PRIMARY AIRCRAFT STRUCTURE

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SUMMARY: Repairs based on adhesively bonded fibre composite patches or reinforcements are standard procedure for repairing mechanical damage in thin-skinned graphite/epoxy and are becoming widely accepted for repairing cracks, corrosion and other defects in aluminium alloy airframe structure. However, bonded composite repairs although often more cost effective and efficient than mechanically fastened patch repairs, and thus a promising technology for extending the life of ageing aircraft, are generally limited to non-primary structure and to non-critical damage in primary structure. Perhaps the major obstacle to the application of bonded composite repairs to critical damage in primary structure is the cost of airworthiness certification.

This paper discusses the critical issues in the certification in bonded repairs to primary structure and suggests a generic approach to minimise costs. Two case histories are described as examples: one a boron/epoxy repair to an F111 aluminium alloy wing skin the other a demonstrator scarf repair to a F/A-18 graphite/epoxy stabilator. Finally, the "Smart Patch" concept is discussed and an early attempt for using this approach to monitor in-service structural integrity of a critical boron/epoxy reinforcement of the F111 wing pivot fitting is described.

KEYWORDS: bonded repairs, certification; ageing aircraft; smart patches

INTRODUCTION

Repairs for graphite/epoxy (gr/ep) or aluminium alloy airframe components based on adhesively bonded composite reinforcements or patches are far more effective in restoring strength than repairs based on mechanically fastened metallic patches [1,2].

However, application of bonded composite repair technology to primary structure, although often highly feasible, is generally acceptable only on the basis that design limit-load (DLL) capability is retained in the loss (total failure) of the repair [3]; DLL is usually the maximum load expected in the life of the airframe. Thus the repair is essentially required to restore the safety margin to design ultimate load (DUL), usually $1.5 \times \text{DLL}$.

Whilst the DLL limitation is obviously safe and minimises certification requirements it will result in the scrapping of many expensive, yet potentially repairable components. Further, the implications of the DLL restriction are potentially far more limiting for repair situations where damage growth is possible [4] even though static strength of the repair is initially above DLL. The implications in this case are that inspection intervals must be based on the predicted rate of damage growth from the unrepaired damage. The related issue of damage tolerance requirements is considered later.

BONDED COMPOSITE REPAIRS TO METALS

Figures 1a) and b) highlight some of the major disadvantages of mechanical repairs to cracks and advantages of bonded repairs based on boron/epoxy (b/ep). The important point is that bonded repairs provide a far more effective reinforcement than mechanical repairs so that “live” (untreated) cracks can be left in the structure. Mechanical repairs require the removal of the cracked region and also the introduction of extra fastener holes. Both of these requirements are costly, highly intrusive, and potentially damaging to the structure and substructure. Swift [5] shows that mechanical patch repairs unless very carefully designed can significantly reduce fatigue life.

Figure 1: a) Some disadvantages of standard mechanically fastened repairs and b) advantages of bonded composite repairs.

Compared to metals, advanced fibre composites such as b/ep and gr/ep have the advantages for making patches or reinforcements of formability, tailorability of stiffness, high specific strength and stiffness, and immunity to corrosion or fatigue. Composite patches or reinforcements can be pre-cured and secondarily bonded (first pre-formed and then bonded) or cocured (cured with the repair adhesive) directly on the structure.

In addition to cracking, critical damage includes pitting or exfoliation corrosion. Bonded composite repairs, based on b/ep or gr/ep patches are very effective for all of these damage types [6]. Bonded composite doublers can also be used very effectively to reduce fatigue strain in regions prone to cracking or simply to replace material lost by corrosion damage.

The scope of bonded composites to repair or reinforce metallic structure can be summarised as follows:

Reduce Stress Intensity

in regions with fatigue cracks

in regions with stress corrosion cracks

to increase damage tolerance (provide slow crack growth characteristics) in safe life structure, this may be cracked or uncracked

Restore Strength and Stiffness

after removal of corrosion damage below allowable limits

after removal of flaws, for example those produced during manufacture

Stiffen Underdesigned Regions to

- reduce strain and increase fatigue life
- remove strain concentrations, including that due to secondary bending
- reduce vibration and acoustic damage

The use of bonded composites (mainly b/ep) to repair cracking and other defects in aluminium airframe structures has been pioneered and extensively developed in Australia. Applications to primary structure (mostly in Royal Australian Air Force aircraft) include:

C130 Wings	- stress-corrosion cracks in wing risers
Mirage III Wings	- fatigue cracks in wing skin
F111-C Wing	- reduce strain in high-strength steel wing pivot fitting
F111-C Wing	- fatigue crack above critical size in wing skin
C141 Wings (USAF)*	- fatigue cracks from fuel weep holes in wing risers
Boeing 767 Keel Beam	- severe corrosion damage (has FAA Type Certification)
F/A-18 Bulkhead	- reduce fatigue strain in wing attachment bulkhead

The repair shown boxed is the only bonded composite repair undertaken in Australia to date where the cracked component would not withstand DLL in the absence of the repair; this is discussed as a case study later.

BONDED COMPOSITE REPAIR OF COMPOSITES

Critical service damage in gr/ep airframe components generally results from mechanical impact, which when severe causes extensive trans-ply cracking, inter-ply delaminations and fibre fractures. Other serious service damage includes major delaminations due to unexpected through-thickness loading and local matrix degradation due to overheating or lightning burn.

Because of the rapid rate of impact damage growth in composites (at high strain levels) the damaged region is generally removed prior to patch repair; however, there is an option to leave some or all of the damage to minimise the removal of sound material. Figure 2a and b shows some typical repairs to composite components.

Figure 2: Typical bonded composite airframe repairs to honeycomb sandwich components a) external patch repair of thin-skinned and b) scarf repair of thick-skinned primary structure.

Repairs [7,8] based on external gr/ep composite patches, Figure 2 a) (or thin titanium sheet) are standard for relatively thin gr/ep (generally honeycomb cored) components and pose no

* With licensee companies: Helitech Australia, Composites Technology Inc. USA, and Advanced Repair Technology Inc. (ARTI), USA.

major structural problems. Scarf repairs, Figure 2 b) are an alternative to externally bolted titanium (or sometimes aluminium alloy or composite) patches for repair of highly-loaded thick-skinned gr/ep. Scarf repairs are much more effective in restoring strength than bolted repairs but large areas of skin removal must be made in thick parent structure to develop the required scarf angle, generally about 3° . Generally scarf repairs are made only to thick-skinned honeycomb or integrally stiffened structures, as mechanical repairs provide adequate static and fatigue strength recovery in structure already joined by mechanical fastening. In contrast to the fatigue problems with metals, discussed earlier, the introduction of new fastener holes is not generally a concern with composite structures.

CLASSIFICATION OF AIRCRAFT STRUCTURES FOR INSPECTION AND REPAIR

For the purpose of engineering management, aircraft structures are generally classified as follows:

Primary: Structure critical to the safety of the aircraft;

Secondary: Structure that, if it were to fail, would affect the operation of the aircraft but not lead to its loss;

Tertiary: Structure in which failure would not significantly affect operation of the aircraft.

Inspection, damage assessment, and repair requirements, differ significantly between these classifications. Even within a single component the allowable damage type and size (and consequently acceptable repair actions) will vary according to the criticality of the damaged region. The component is generally zoned by the Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) in the Structural Repair Manual (SRM) to indicate these regions. Mainly, the SRM addresses repairs to non-primary structure or non-critical repairs to primary structure. Repairs outside the scope of the SRM, particularly to critical regions of primary structure, require engineering design and approval by the OEM (or its delegate).

Essentially, certification of repairs to primary structure requires demonstration that the repaired structure is as flight worthy as the original structure, possibly allowing for life already consumed. Further, according to the latest regulations, such as FAR 25.571 (for civil aircraft), there is now a need to demonstrate that the repaired structure is damage-tolerant, even if the original structure was designed on a safe life basis.

While it is possible to demonstrate that these requirements are met by testing closely representative repaired structure under simulated service loading and environmental conditions, the challenge is to accomplish it (at least to a large extent) on a generic basis. If this is not possible many technically feasible repairs to primary structure will not be cost effective. Thus it is the purpose of this paper to discuss how a (largely) generic repair approach may be developed for bonded composite repairs to primary structure. The approach proposed here largely follows current procedures for certifying new structure.

CERTIFICATION APPROACHES FOR METALLIC AIRCRAFT STRUCTURE

Typically, certification for new metallic structures requires that the airframe structure (by test and or analysis) must demonstrate the following capabilities:

Static Strength:

DLL no failure or unacceptable deformations

DUL no failure although permanent deformation is acceptable; $DUL = DLL \times 1.5$
(generally)

Fatigue:

Safe life: no cracking which could lead to failure for the life of the airframe.

or

Fail safe: cracking may occur but will not reduce strength below acceptable level before being detected. This approach is generally based on multi-load-path structure.

or

Damage tolerant: cracking may occur but will grow slowly and will not cause failure for the full life of the structure or before detection (safety by inspection). Damage tolerant design is often based on the assumed presence of flaws at critical locations at the start of life.

Damage Tolerance:

The strength will not fall below an acceptable level (typically $1.2 \times DLL$) due to representative damage to the structure, eg caused by fatigue cracking, or corrosion before being detected. Critical damage must be of a size that can be detected with a high degree of probability.

Durability:

For the life of the airframe damage requiring costly repairs will not occur for example, due to fatigue or corrosion.

The requirements for composites (and to some extent for bonded structure) are broadly similar [9] but must account for several differences in behaviour [10] including:

Resistance to fatigue (flat S/N curve) but high scatter and damage growth rate.

Sensitivity to out-of-plane loads.

Sensitivity to hot/wet environment.

Sensitivity to mechanical (impact) damage.

Design of the airframe involves firstly a detailed structural analysis, usually using a structural finite-element (F-E) model and secondly a test program on specimens of increasing complexity from simple coupons to structural simulations and full-scale structures [11]. Coupon and structural element (also called structural feature) tests are used to obtain material and structural allowables for design and must therefore interrogate all critical loading conditions and potential failure modes; the other tests are essentially for proof of structure. These specimens (shown schematically) fulfil the following requirements:

Coupons: $L \approx 0.1\text{m}$; $N \approx (\text{test number}) 400$
 -generate generic materials data base
 eg materials **A** and **B** allowables

Structural Elements: $L \approx 0.2\text{m}$; $N \approx 50$
 Generate generic feature data base
 represent all potential failure modes
 check calculation rules

Structural Details: $L \approx 1\text{m}$; $N \approx 10$
 Generate non-generic design values
 check damage tolerance

Sub-Component: $L \approx 3\text{m}$; $N \approx 4$
 Check for unexpected failure modes
 compare with detail and element tests

Component: $L \approx 15\text{m}$; $N \approx 2$
 Check strain levels against failure strains
 demonstrate airworthiness compliance

Aircraft: $L \approx 30\text{m}$; $N \approx 1$
 Demonstrate airworthiness compliance

Similar requirements can be stated for repairs which can be considered as new structure. The damage tolerance requirements are particularly significant when damage is allowed to remain in the parent structure.

Before considering in more detail the certification of repairs, which have similar requirements, the issue of the design allowables is discussed in the next section.

DESIGN ALLOWABLES

Strength

The development of design allowables from coupons and structural features is a very important and costly component of the design and certification process. Design allowables will also be needed for design of repairs particularly when made to primary structure. Mil Handbooks 5 and 17 set out, respectively, the statistical requirements and estimating procedures for metals and composites.

Briefly, airframe design is based on coupon and structural element data which allows for statistical variation or scatter in strength. Two allowable values are generally estimated:

A-allowable: value achieved by 99% of the population at the 99% confidence level

B-allowable: value achieved by 90% of the population at the 95% confidence level

To determine these allowables the statistical model which best fits the property distribution is first determined. For metals the distribution is generally normal or (often for fatigue) log normal. When dealing with composites the first model evaluated is the two-parameter Weibull distribution (as it is a physically more realistic model for brittle materials) followed by the normal and then the log normal.

An important economic aspect in testing is the estimation [12] of the minimum number of specimens which need to be tested to obtain acceptable allowables. This depends on the

statistical parameters. Testing can be reduced significantly if the distribution parameters are already known. For example, it has been shown [10] that the shape parameter for the Weibull distribution for strength of composites and metals is generally around 35 and 20 respectively, corresponding to coefficients of variation of 3.5% and 6.5%.

The choice of which allowable to work with depends on the particular application. For materials with a low scatter, such as airframe alloys, the **A**-allowable strength is often used since this obviously offers the greatest margin of safety, but in cases where scatter is large this may impose too great a penalty on useable strength. The **B**-allowable strength is also appropriate for fail-safe or multiple load-path design. For composites the **B**-allowable is generally used because of the relatively high scatter on strength.

Because of the costly specimen testing requirements to obtain **A** or **B** allowables “knockdown factors” can be used to reduce the allowables which would allow for variations in strength properties, for example with metals due to temperature changes. This approach essentially assumes that the coefficient of variation is unchanged by the variable. For composites and bonded structure knockdown factors can be determined for hot/wet conditions. The effect of representative flaws and defects in structural features can also be covered by this approach.

Fatigue Life

The main aim of the component fatigue test is to demonstrate with an acceptable level of probability that failure of the aircraft structure will not occur at the design stress; this stress corresponds with the **B**-allowable fatigue strength found from the coupon and structural element tests and is the allowed maximum stress at DLL, the highest stress in the spectrum. For development of the fatigue allowables (life and residual strength) coupons and structural elements, are tested under spectrum loading, representative of expected service conditions. The affect of representative damage will generally be evaluated on structural elements and structural features. S/N curves of coupons and structural elements may also be determined under constant amplitude cycling to obtain basic data for assessment of spectrum loading behaviour and to establish load discrimination levels.

The main feature of fatigue is that scatter is significantly greater than for most other mechanical properties so many more of these time-consuming tests are required to obtain the allowable values. Fibre composites have an even greater scatter in fatigue lives than metals as they are highly resistant to fatigue [10]. For example the shape coefficients in the Weibull distribution for fatigue of metals and composites are generally 1.25 and 7.5 respectively [13] corresponding with coefficients of variation of around 80% and 15% respectively.

The use of load enhancement to reduce testing times and to minimise the need for hot/wet testing of composite components is discussed in references [13] and [14].

Damage Growth

A knowledge of the critical dimensions of damage for catastrophic growth and rate of growth to critical size are the basic requirements for damage tolerance designs.

Cracking is the main damage of concern for metals and allowables (eg critical crack size and growth rate) are based on linear elastic fracture mechanics approaches. The information on crack growth rate is used to set inspection intervals. Generally for metals the rate of crack

growth $da/dn \propto \Delta G^n$ where ΔG is the range of strain energy release rate and n an empirical exponent, usually between 1.4 and 2.

For composites (and bonded structures) disbonds and delaminations are the main damage types of concern and growth rate can be rapid above the (high) damage initiation threshold. Typically the exponent n for damage growth of fatigue damage is 4 to 5, although it can be lower for loading configurations having low peel stresses.

Thus for composites the approach is to specify as a **B**-allowable the stress at the threshold for damage growth. This is generally determined from coupons with pre-existing visible damage (such as a small indentation [10]); design allowables based on growth of non-visible damage are generally unacceptable. Thus essentially a safe life approach to damage tolerance is taken.

REQUIREMENTS FOR CERTIFICATION OF BONDED COMPOSITE REPAIRS

Repairs to Cracked Metallic Structure (Slow Damage Growth in Parent)

Based, in part, on the recommendations provided in reference 3 (based on FAR 25.571 for damage tolerant repairs, as mentioned earlier) it was proposed [6] that certification should be on the basis of demonstration by analysis and/or test that the repair meets the following requirements [modified further here]:

Residual Strength

Provide a minimum residual strength of $1.5 \times$ DLL or some other acceptable factor (often around 1.2) times DLL under the temperature and environmental conditions in which the aircraft is operated.

Retain this level of residual strength in the repair region through the remaining life of the airframe or for a suitable period - ideally coinciding with the requirements for the undamaged structure.

Minimise strain elevation in adjacent sound structure to avoid life reduction.

Damage Tolerance [15]

Provide zero or very slow (predictable) crack growth from the pre-existing crack. Even if the crack emerges from under the patch (due, for example, to faulty inspection), it must be shown that growth will be slow enough to be detected during the next scheduled inspection.

Allow easy high-reliability detection of the crack by standard NDI ultrasonic or eddy-current procedures (patch should be transparent to NDI of parent structure).

Be insensitive to flaws including disbonds and impact damage.

Durability

Be highly resistant to minor disbonding or other local degradation of the patch system that would require frequent patch maintenance or replacement.

Repairs to Composite Structure (Rapid Damage Growth in Parent)

Similar requirements apply to repairs to composites with one major exception. This is that the damage tolerance requirements for slow damage growth in the parent structure are usually not applicable, since as previously discussed damage growth in composites can be very rapid. Generally, the pre-existing damage will have been removed and the situation is simply that of dealing with the threshold for damage growth from a reinforced cut-out. However, there is the option of leaving some damage, such as minor delaminations if it can be shown that the

rate of damage growth is low. This situation may apply where minor delaminations are left under a relatively stiff doubler able to suppress mode 1 peel stresses. Generally, however, repairs to composites will need to be certified using a safe-life approach on the basis that strains are kept below a damage threshold.

Reinforcement versus Repair

In many bonded composite repair applications to primary structure (including the F111 wing pivot fitting discussed later) the aim is simply to reduce strain before the onset of critical damage. In this application since the structure is essentially unmodified (no damage or cut-outs) the certification requirements are somewhat less stringent since the structure in the absence (failure of) of the reinforcement is still able to carry the design loads.

ISSUES AND PROPOSED APPROACHES FOR CERTIFICATION

Assurance of Bond Environmental Durability - *The Crucial Issue*

Without doubt the most crucial need for bonded repairs is to establish with a high level of confidence that no catastrophic disbonding of the reinforcement can occur due to environmental degradation or to service loading. In the absence of this assurance all other engineering estimations are meaningless. The use of proven surface treatment and bonding processes (suitable for use in repair situations) together with high-level quality control procedures [16], including technician training, are the only effective means of providing confidence that environmental degradation will not be a concern, since there is currently no effective NDI procedure for assessing bond durability (and unlikely to be in the foreseeable future), all that can be detected are fairly gross voids and disbonds.

Considerable effort has been devoted in Australia to the development of *in-situ* bonding surface treatments for metals and composites which are: simple, versatile to apply, effective, non-specific, low risk (tolerant to adverse environments) and non-hazardous. Simplicity, tolerance and low risk are very important since repairs are often performed in difficult situations and adverse environments.

Fortunately for epoxy-matrix composites, simple ceramic grit blasting is an optimised surface treatment process, even for factory usage; however, for metals more complex chemical treatments are required. While *in-situ* surface treatments specifically for aluminium alloys based on phosphoric acid anodising are the most effective in providing bond durability they lack versatility and tolerance. Australian work [2,17] has concentrated on the use of coupling agents (epoxy-compatible silanes) following grit blasting. This process has the desired attributes (including ability to treat titanium alloys and steel) and provides adequate bond durability, as judged from laboratory tests and confirmed by Australian service experience.

The proposed requirements and approaches to assure a high level of quality control in the environmental durability of bonded repairs (focusing on metals) are provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Bond environmental durability assurance approaches

Requirement	Approach
<p>To ensure high confidence in repair bond durability</p> <p>The graph plots Crack length (mm) on the y-axis (25 to 40) against Time (Hours) on a logarithmic x-axis (1 to 1000). Treatment A (circles) shows a sharp increase in crack length starting around 100 hours, reaching approximately 37 mm at 1000 hours. Treatment B (squares) shows a much slower increase, reaching only about 29 mm at 1000 hours. An inset shows a wedge coupon test setup under 50°C +100% RH conditions.</p>	<p>Undertake Process Evaluation: Evaluate repair treatments (shown inset, based on Boeing wedge test) Benchmark against factory treatment assess process window</p> <p>Develop Quality Procedures [18], including: training and qualifying technicians develop process documentation make/test traveller repair wedge coupons</p>

Development of Generic Patch System Design Allowables

To guard against failure in the patch system due to service loading the design approach is to ensure shear and peel strains in the adhesive and patch, particularly at the ends of the reinforcement, Figure 3, are maintained below the damage initiation threshold since disbond growth in this region can be rapid. This is achieved [19,2] by limiting strains in the critical regions by design (eg appropriate end tapering) and use of appropriate strain allowables.

Figure 3: Illustration of an external bonded patch showing safe life zone (no cracking allowed in patch system) and damage tolerance zone (slow crack growth allowed in patch system).

Even slow initial disbond growth in the end region is unacceptable since once the disbond reaches the inner end of the taper region peel and shear strains dramatically increase and

growth will become rapid. Thus the patch system in this region must be designed on a safe life basis.

However, for an external patch, limited disbond growth in the patch system (usually the highest stress region) is acceptable over the damage region in the parent structure, Figure 3, as this is generally slow (peel stresses are low or negative) and has only a small effect on reinforcing efficiency [6].

Following the approach for new structures, repair design allowables are obtained from tests on coupons and generic structural features- in this case generic bonded joints:

Coupon tests, mainly to obtain adhesive and composite static strength/strain (and possibly also fatigue) allowables, as indicated in Table 2.

Table 2: Coupon test program for process and quality control

Requirement	Approach
<p>To obtain data base for static strength of repair materials <i>eg for adhesive shear stress/strain:</i></p>	<p>Undertake adhesive tests (short over-lap shear test shown inset) to obtain:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> B basis allowables for yield and failure shear strains B basis allowable strain range for fatigue damage initiation N cycles, constant amplitude <p>Undertake composite tests to obtain:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> B basis allowables for static failure strain in a simple joint configuration <p>Obtain for both knock-down factors for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> hot/wet conditions strain rate/creep effects (adhesive) off-optimum cure etc

Generic bonded joints mainly to obtain the reinforcement system fatigue allowables; however, they can also provide effective adhesive properties in place of the coupon tests.

The proposed tests are outlined in Table 3.

Table 3: Generic joint test program to obtain repair system allowables

Requirement	Approach
<p>To find joint static and fatigue strain allowables and confirm validity of failure criteria based on coupon test data.</p> <p><i>The failure criteria must hold for similar geometrical configurations, eg adherend thickness and stiffness and adhesive thickness.</i></p> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Generic Double Overlap joint</p> <p>Generic Scarf Joint</p> </div>	<p>Undertake static strength tests to: check strength against predictions based on coupon data</p> <p>Undertake fatigue tests to: obtain B-basis threshold for fatigue disbond growth rate of disbond growth at constant amplitude and spectrum loading</p> <p>Find knockdown factors for: hot/wet conditions non-optimum manufacture representative damage</p>

As an example, tests are in progress to measure the threshold for disbond initiation and growth rate in generic bonded joints representing b/ep patch repairs to aluminium alloy specimen; shown inset in Figure 4.

The approach being evaluated is to use the theoretical or the measured strain range in the adhesive $\Delta\gamma$ as the damage severity criteria and plot this against disbond growth rate db/dN , as shown in Figure 4. The dotted line is arbitrarily defined as the initiation threshold in this case.

Figure 4: Plot of disbond growth rate in the adhesive versus shear strain range obtained from tests on a double overlap joint, shown inset. The adhesive is FM73, around 0.3mm thick, the inner adherend is 2024T6 aluminium, around 3mm thick, and the outer adherends are b/ep, around 1mm thick.

Generic Structural Detail Tests - Validation of Repair Models

The aim of this program is mainly to validate design approaches for generic repair configurations and to assess damage tolerance. This program is based on tests on a range of generic structural detail specimens, as indicated in Table 4.

Table 4: Validation of design approaches based on generic structural detail program

Requirement	Approach
Validate (F-E ²⁰ /analytical ²²) design procedures and assess repair damage tolerance Generic Scarf Patch	Undertake tests to assess: Static strength under various environments Fatigue strength, threshold for damage initiation in patch system Threshold for growth and rate of growth of residual damage, eg cracks in metals Influence of spectrum loading and environment Assess damage tolerance: Residual strength before and after fatigue damage to patch system and residual damage Influence of impact damage to patch and deliberate disbonds in patch system

Work on generic repair structural detail specimens (patched metallic specimens) has been in progress for some time in Australia [21]. Figure 5 a) depicts the specimen tested and Figure 5 b) plots results which help to validate the analytical patching model [22] used.

Figure 5: a) Generic structural detail test specimen for patched cracks in metallic structures used to validate the patching model and b) plot of experimental log da/dN versus log ΔK , obtained from the analytical patching model.

PROPOSED REPAIR CERTIFICATION APPROACH

The steps, as set out in Table 5, are i) undertake preliminary design using the data base and validated model from the generic test program, ii) identify by detailed F-E or other analysis how the specific repair differs from the generic case and ii) develop and validate the final design based on tests which interrogate only these differences.

Table 5: Outline of the approach proposed for repair certification

Step	Approach
Qualification of processes and repair materials	Follow prescribed quality procedures
Obtain stress information eg DUL and fatigue spectrum load etc	Obtain OEM design data for DUL etc. Fatigue spectrum (military aircraft) best obtained from instrumented aircraft, if available
Preliminary feasibility assessment and design of repair based on generic data and patching model	Use allowables data from generic coupons and repair joints. Base design on validated model from generic studies
Design representative bonded joint to interrogate differences (if any) with generic repair	Use detailed F-E model of actual repair, to design representative joint specimens
Test representative bonded joints to check safety margin of repair joint 	Test sufficient representative bonded joints to obtain indication of fatigue performance compared with generic joint. Test at constant amplitude up to DLL level

Step	Approach
Finalise design of repair, based on new data, and check performance 	Test representative structural details under spectrum loading, ambient and representative hot/wet conditions. <i>Could use elevated load at a level based on representative bonded joint hot/wet tests</i> <i>May not need to do this test if differences with generic structural detail specimen are not too great</i>
Check for unexpected secondary stresses <i>For example due to neutral axis offset bending or to strain concentration in adjacent structure</i> 	Static strain survey on instrumented sub-component specimen may be adequate to check similarity to structural detail. <i>Could be done on actual repair in some cases</i> <i>Optional additional testing under spectrum loading,</i>

CASE HISTORIES

Two case histories are presented here as (imperfect) examples of the proposed approach. The first is an real repair developed for a critical fatigue crack in the aluminium alloy lower wing skin of an F111 and the second is a demonstrator repair to a gr/ep skin in an F/A-18 horizontal stabilator.

Bonded Composite Repair to F111 Lower Wing Skin [23]

The need for this repair followed the discovery of a 48 mm long fatigue crack in the lower wing skin (aluminium alloy 2024-T851) of an F111 aircraft. Preliminary fracture mechanics calculations indicated that the residual strength had been degraded to 168 MPa, which is considerably less than the Design Ultimate Stress of 358 MPa specified for this region of the wing.

The cracking arises because of the local geometry of the wing skin at the site of cracking which gives rise to a significant stress concentration coupled with secondary bending.

A repair based on a mechanically fastened metallic doubler was initially considered, but this repair option was discarded because of poor fatigue properties, poor inspectability and undesirable aerodynamic implications. Thus, the only viable alternative to a bonded repair would have been scrapping the wing.

This repair has several features which are particularly significant for the certification of critical bonded repairs to primary structure. The most important being that the crack reduced the residual strength below the specified Design Limit Stress of 238 MPa, compromising safety-of-flight. Thus, the implementation and approval of any repair option required very stringent scrutiny. Indeed, from the viewpoint of demonstrating compliance with certification requirements, this repair can claim to be the most technically challenging bonded repair yet undertaken by the RAAF and most likely by any organisation.

An important issue for this repair is that the local geometry (responsible for the cracking) also results in the development of significant peel stresses in the adhesive, in addition to the usual shear stresses resulting from load transfer into the patch. Thus the stressing differs somewhat from the generic repair studied and this was taken into account in the certification program.

The verification program had to be more extensive than desirable because some of the generic information required was not available. However, had this information been available, along the lines discussed, the effort required to substantiate this repair would have been markedly reduced. Generally the approach followed the steps set out in Table 6.

Table 6: Outline of F111 wing skin repair certification program, continued on next page

Activity	Approach
Establish critical static load cases and fatigue spectrum	Manufacturer's information indicated a DUL of 358 MPa. Fatigue load spectrum at the wing root was available through the F111 Australian ASIP program
Establish stresses in the cracked region.	Undertook F-E analysis of the region before and after patching and calibrated with experimental strain survey. <i>Noted high peel component in patch</i>
Preliminary design of patch 	Based on patching allowables from generic joint tests and RAAF Engineering Standard [18,24], Tables 4 and 5 <i>Fig shows location of cracking on the F111 lower wing-skin inner surface showing also the outline of the repair patch made of 14 ply b/ep (0₂, ± 45, 0₃)_S bonded with adhesive FM73 around 500 mm spanwise × 350 mm chordwise.</i>
Verify patch design 	Using F-E analysis the design was checked and found to be acceptable, despite complications due to peel Predicted patching performance was checked against the generic model <i>Fig shows predictions of 3D finite-element model of the region compared with strain gauge readings. The strain reduction on the outside surface results from the secondary bending which, correspondingly, causes a marked strain elevation on the inside surface - resulting in the fatigue cracking</i>
Design representative joint and structural detail specimen	Using F-E model to check that stress distribution corresponds with that for repaired structure
Verify patching allowables. 	Test a representative bonded joint under a range of environmental and fatigue conditions [25] <i>To check the influence of the peel component compared with the generic bonded joint</i>

Table 6: Outline of F111 wing skin repair certification program.

Activity	Approach
<p>Assess residual static strength and crack growth rate in the patch system</p>	
<p>Confirm repair efficiency and influence of patch on strain levels in surrounding structure</p>	

F/A-18 HORIZONTAL STABILATOR [26]

An F/A-18 horizontal stabilator (gr/ep skins AS4/3501-6, on a heavy aluminium alloy honeycomb core) suffered impact damage near the spindle attachment point in a high-strain region (from around 7 to 32 plies thick), and was therefore deemed by the OEM to be unreparable. While most of the design ultimate strains in the stabilator are around 3750 microstrain ($\mu\epsilon$) the peak design ultimate strain close to the spindle was stated to be very high, around 5200 $\mu\epsilon$.

To evaluate the effectiveness of scarf repairs to such a highly strained structure, a research program was undertaken based on representative joint tests and the damaged and repaired stabilator. This program was simply a feasibility study for a very challenging repair; however, for the purpose of this discussion it is considered as part of a certification evaluation - with the missing aspects noted. The overall program is as shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Outline of the F/A-18 gr/ep horizontal stabilator repair program, continued on next page

Activity	Approach
<p>Establish critical strains for component test</p> <p>Design representative joint</p>	<p>Obtained from F-E analysis provided by OEM.</p> <p>Based on Northrop approach using very limited materials allowables data.</p> <p><i>An extensive coupon and generic joint test program was needed to establish B-allowable adhesive strain, particularly fatigue threshold, and knock-down factors for hot/wet environment non-optimum manufacture</i></p>
<p>Establish residual strength of the representative joint.</p>	<p>Test representative joints, to measure ultimate failure strain in the skin to +104°C, -40°C and to evaluate ultimate failure strain following impact damage and cyclic loading</p> <p><i>Data from generic joints unavailable, would have minimised test program if available</i></p> <p><i>Strength of scarf under hot/wet conditions found to be marginal; critical in the adhesive layer</i></p> <p><i>Found potential adhesive creep problem</i></p> <p><i>Joint tolerant to fatigue at constant amplitude cycling at DLL and under spectrum loading</i></p> <p><i>Preliminary tests suggest impact resistance good</i></p>
<p>Final design and validation testing</p>	<p>Not undertaken in this program but required</p> <p><i>Only few tests needed on a representative structural detail specimen if a good generic data base had been available</i></p> <p><i>This test may have provided more optimistic result as alternate load path allows load redistribution due to creep, etc and unloads adhesive. Essentially some load can be carried around hole by undamaged material</i></p>

Table 7: Outline of the F/A-18 gr/ep horizontal stabilator repair program.

Activity	Approach
<p>Test fully instrumented component to DLL to establish if allowable strains at design ultimate hot/wet <u>would have been exceeded</u>.</p> <p><i>Repair implemented by US Navy to Northrop specification.</i></p>	<p>Strains to a maximum of 5200 microstrain found at DUL by extrapolation, as specified by OEM and predicted by our F-E analysis²⁷.</p> <p><i>This confirmed that representative joint results were not sufficiently high, allowing for knock-down factors.</i></p> <p><i>However, structural detail tests if undertaken may have altered this conclusion</i></p>

“SMART PATCH” APPROACH: F111 WING PIVOT B/EP DOUBLER

For the certification and management of critical repairs for very high cost components the “Smart Patch” approach may be acceptable from the airworthiness perspective and be cost effective for the operator and may even allow some relaxation of the certification requirements. In the most elementary application of smart patches, (which could also be called *in situ* NDI) sensors are used as a nerve system to monitor in service the structural condition (health) of the patch system and the status of any remaining damage in the parent structure. The sensors, which may for example be resistance [28] or piezoelectric strain gauges or optical fibres [29,30], are ideally (for robustness) embedded in the composite patch or more simply bonded to its surface.

Figure 6: Schematic showing above location of critical area in the F111 wing pivot fitting and below detail of the critical area and b/ep doubler, over 120 plies (16mm) thick.

The specific objectives, referring to Figure 3, are to detect disbond growth in the safe life zone of the patch (which is unacceptable) and monitor damage growth in the parent material (below the damage tolerance zone) - delaminations for composites or cracks for metals. The smart patch approach for detecting disbond growth in a repair system during service operation was planned for in-service management of a large (120+ ply thick) b/ep doubler reinforcement for the wing pivot fitting (WPF) of Australian F111 aircraft.

Fatigue cracks can initiate in the upper-skin of the F111 Wing Pivot Fitting (WPF) stiffener runout region shown in Figure 6. Initiation of cracks in this highly-stressed D6ac steel component can be traced back to plastic yielding in this region which occurs during the (severe) Cold Proof Load Test (CPLT) which the aircraft periodically undergoes to screen for small cracks. Residual tensile stresses developed as a result of the yielding can lead to crack-initiation and catastrophic failure in flight or (more likely) during a subsequent CPLT. A strain reduction of over 30 % is required to avoid plastic yielding in this region [31] and also to increase the in-service inspection interval. The required strain reduction is particularly challenging because of the thick steel structure and high loading. To achieve the required strain reduction without causing damage to the structure, b/ep doublers, as depicted in Figure 6, were designed and developed [28,32].

The approach taken was to apply external resistance strain gauges on the ends of the taper on the b/ep doubler and on the surface of the steel WPF away from the doubler and monitor the ratio (doubler strains) / (strain in the steel fitting) during service life. Any decrease in this ratio is an indication of disbonding of the doubler. It is important to note there is no requirement in this approach for measurement of the loading. A similar approach is being used [33] to monitor the structural integrity of a large (5m × 1m) 6mm thick doubler used to reduce cracking around welds in the aluminium deck of an Royal Australian Navy Frigate.

Figure 7 shows results obtained from tests on an F111 representative bonded joint specimen (representing a section through the doubler) subjected to CPLT loads and the F111 loading spectrum.

Figure 7: Plot of strain ratio reduction due to disbond growth as a result of fatigue cycling and above representative bonded joint specimen showing strain gauge positions. The F gauge results plotted are on the corners of the doubler.

Disbonding is indicated by the reduction in relative strain, as shown in Figure 7. The disbands initiated and grew mainly from the corners of the doubler at the ends of the taper growth was very much less in the centre. In the aircraft doubler system the sides are tapered normal to the doubler axis, so stress concentrations in these corners will be much less severe; however, the results show the effectiveness of the monitoring approach proposed.

This early attempt at in-service monitoring of the doubler gauges (using strain gauge wiring passing through an over wing fairing which covers the doubler), although highly effective for aircraft undergoing the CPLT, proved too cumbersome to be practical for service use.

Current work is aimed at developing a fully self-contained miniaturised strain gauge bridge and data acquisition system attached to the wing (under the over wing fairing) for storing recent in-flight high-load readings of the strain ratio. The data acquisition data will be read remotely as required using infra-red technology. Alternatively the system could be programmed to provide an early warning when significant changes in strain ratio occur.

A far more sophisticated application of the "Smart Patch" approach is to include both a sensor - nerve system (as just discussed) and a reactive - muscle capability. One application of this technology is for example in the repair of acoustic cracking where the patch can provide both reinforcement (while monitoring its own integrity) and reactive damping. This approach is being evaluated in connection with an acoustic fatigue cracking problem being encountered in the engine inlet case in the F/A-18.

CONCLUDING COMMENTS

An approach for the certification of adhesively bonded composite repairs to primary aircraft structure, metal or composite, is proposed based on the development of a data base from tests on generic structural elements (joints) and generic structural details; the latter being used to validate repair design models. Tests on representative structure is limited mainly to evaluating only those aspects in which the actual repair differs from the generic configuration. This approach requires a very good analytical capability to assess the differences and to design appropriate test specimens. A somewhat similar approach is suggested by Hall [34] et al for repairs to composite primary structure.

The crucial requirements for repair bonding are highlighted: This requires the use of effective bonding processes together with a high level of quality control.

Two case histories are briefly described as examples of the proposed approach: one a b/ep patch repair to an F111 aluminium alloy wing skin and the other a demonstrator scarf repair to an F/A-18 gr/ep stabilator.

The concept of the "Smart Patch," a patch able to monitor its own structural integrity, is described and an early attempt to incorporate this approach on a massive b/ep doubler developed to reinforce the high-strength steel wing pivot fitting on F111 is discussed.

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